

Casanova *Drift Model* (CDM)

A mechanistic spray drift model
for ground application of plant
protection products

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We Need A Higher Tier Ground Drift Model!

EAD Agricultural Buffer Zone Workbook

This workbook allows evaluators to calculate buffer zones for ground-based applications and allows for the input of aerial application data. Buffer zones can be calculated for up to 10 combinations. For each crop/pest combination, buffer zones are individually calculated for user-defined application rates and intervals. The cumulative (or largest) buffer zone for each crop is then placed on the product label. If you require buffer zones for more than ten crops, there is a separate workbook for that purpose.

Mitteilungen aus der Biologischen Bundesanstalt
für Land- und Forstwirtschaft
Berlin-Dahlem

Studies on the spray drift of plant protection
the

by
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AGDISP

Tier I Models/
Spreadsheets/
Drift Tables

OR

Field Studies

AgDISP frequently overpredicts (>1000 ft) for distance to no effect!!!

Higher Tier Ground Model: Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Develop

- Developed “ground up”
- Lagrangian tracking in space and time
- Detailed wind profile, canopy effects
- Incorporates wind turbulence
- Nozzle characteristics
- Droplet evaporation

Validate

- Spray drift task force
- SETAC DRAW
- Bayer internal trials

Consult

- Milt Teske, Continuum
- Paul Miller, Silsoe

Outreach

- Expert Testing
- Presentations
 - ACS 2021, Virtual
 - IAPA 2022, Germany

Higher Tier Ground Model: Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Spray Drift Is A Complex, Multi-Factorial Phenomenon

CDM Has 7 Major Components

1 DSD Fit

- Droplet size distribution (DSD)
- Using actual data as opposed to a fit

2 Initial drop velocity

- Nozzle type
- Flow rate
- Angle
- Pressure

3 Tank Mix

- Density
- Active fraction
- Non-volatile
- Dissolved solids

4 Droplet Evaporation

- Wet bulb depression temperature
- Turbulence around droplet

5 Wind

- Vertical profile
- Canopy effects
- Horizontal variation

6 Transport

- Lagrangian
- Tracks droplet position in space and time

7 Deposition

- Downwind segments
- Accumulate droplets for each segment

Lagrangian Equations Track Individual Spray Droplets

Uses Nozzle Spray Angle, Pressure, Flow Rate

Measurement Methods Influence Model Calibration

Drop size distribution (DSD) technique

Laser Vs. Doppler

Sample collection methods

- Petri dishes
- Strings
- Filter pads
- Mylar cards
- Brushes

Uniform crop Vs. non-uniform crop

Future Development

Higher Tier Ground Model: Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Model Validation Projects

1 Sensitivity Analysis

- Nozzles
- Wind Speeds
- Boom Height

2 SDTF

- 17 drift trials
- 3 nozzles

3 Dicamba

- 2015 TX
- TTI/ULD
- UC/C

4 IFT

- 2018 KS
- AIXR 11002
- XC

5 SETAC DRAW

- 13 Trials
- BE, DE, NL, FR
- Various parameters
- Relative Assessment

CDM Accurately Simulates a GLP Spray Drift Trial

CDM Is Predictive of Herbicide Bareground Trial

- AIXR 11002 @ 40 psi – XC nozzle
- 8 – 14 mph wind speed
- Downwind distance: 5, 30, 50, 75, and 100 ft

Lack of Turbulence Data Can Lead to Conservative Predictions

CDM Predicts Higher Far Field Drift at Higher Nozzle Pressure

CDM Predicts Higher Drift at Higher Boom Height

Higher Tier Ground Model: Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Consulting With Modeling Experts To Improve CDM

**Milt,
Teske**

- Developer of AGDISP drift model
- 2-day workshop in 2004
- Detailed discussion on drift and modeling
- Feedback used to strengthen the model

**Paul,
Miller**

- Silsoe Research Institute
- Detailed technical presentation in 2020
- Continual technical exchanges
- Feedback

Higher Tier Ground Model: Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Web-Based Interface Will Support Extensive Expert Testing

Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

[Reset Everything](#)

Choose Dataset
Choose dataset to use
Regulatory Scenarios

Select Regulatory Scenario
Select scenario
Spain

Manually Input or Edit Parameters [Download parameters to file](#)

Environmental Settings

Dry air temperature (Celsius): **16.80455**

Barometric pressure (mmHg abs): **722**

Relative humidity (%): **33.8675**

Application Settings

Density of pure water in droplet (g/cm3): 0.95	Intended Application Rate (kg/ha): 0.57836
Density of dissolved solids in droplet (g/cm3): 1.915143	Concentration in tank solution (wtfraction): 0.011305
Mass fraction total dissolved solids in solution: 0.01881	Downwind field depth (m): 228.152
Height of nozzle above ground (cm): 10	Crosswind field width (m): 749.02

Planning to Consult With Experts to Improve Model and Interface

**Clare,
Butler Ellis**

- Silsoe Research Institute
- Developer of Silsoe Drift Model
- Model/Interface Feedback

**John,
Buonagurio**

- Exponent
- Developer of Sophia model
- Code optimization

**Tom,
Wolf**

- Agrimetrix Research & Training
- Canadian drift expert
- Regulatory knowledge
- Model/interface feedback

**Sean,
Ryan**

- Exponent
- Web optimization
- Interface Development

Planned CDM Enhancements

Turbulence

- Wind turbulence controls droplet dispersion
- 3-D wind data provide improved turbulence characteristics
- Additional turbulence model choices

Wind Profile

- Current model has a single wind profile
- Multiple wind profiles for spray area and downwind

Model Interface

- Source code currently being managed in Gitlab and will be released to the public after expert reviews
- Web-model
 - data from different world regions, and specific expertise from those

Regulatory Scenarios

- Country specific scenarios customized for each regulatory agency
- EU, Canada, US

CDM Fills A Much-Need Regulatory Gap For Spray Drift Risk Assessments

Thank you!

Bye-Bye

